

Transformer-Empowered Actor-Critic Reinforcement Learning for Sequence-Aware Service Function Chain Partitioning

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Abstract—In the forthcoming era of 6G networks, characterized by unprecedented data rates, ultra-low latency, and ubiquitous connectivity, effective management of Virtualized Network Functions (VNFs) is essential. VNFs are software-based counterparts of traditional hardware devices that facilitate flexible and scalable service provisioning. Service Function Chains (SFCs), structured as ordered sequences of VNFs, are pivotal in delivering complex network services. Nevertheless, splitting an SFC into multiple segments that are deployed across different network domains or infrastructure locations presents substantial challenges due to the potential heterogeneity of domain characteristic—such as terrestrial and satellite networks—along with quality of service (QoS) constraints and limited visibility of network state. Conventional optimization-based methods typically exhibit low scalability, whereas existing data-driven approaches often fail to adequately balance computational efficiency with the capability to effectively account for VNF inter-dependencies, inherent in SFCs. To overcome these limitations, we introduce a Transformer-empowered actor-critic framework specifically designed for sequence-aware SFC partitioning. By utilizing the self-attention mechanism, our approach effectively models complex inter-dependencies between VNFs, facilitating coordinated and parallelized decision-making processes. Furthermore, we improve training stability and convergence using the ϵ -LoPe exploration strategy as well as the Asymptotic Return Normalization. Comprehensive simulation results demonstrate that the proposed methodology outperforms existing state-of-the-art solutions in terms of long-term acceptance rates, resource utilization efficiency, and scalability while achieving fast inference. This study not only advances intelligent network orchestration by delivering a scalable and robust solution for SFC partitioning in 6G, but also bridges recent advancements in Large Language Models (LLMs) with the optimization of next-generation networks.

Index Terms—service function chain partitioning, service optimization, network function virtualization, quality of service, zero-touch service orchestration, transformers, deep reinforcement learning

I. INTRODUCTION

THE rapid emergence of beyond 5G and 6G networks has made network slice and logical network abstraction central challenges in the optimization of network resources and services. Network services are forced to compete for a limited resource pool over the shared infrastructure to ensure robust Quality of Service (QoS) and meet stringent Service Level Agreements (SLA). New services not only demand higher cross-domain performance guarantees, but also operate in highly shared, multi-tenant environments, imposing significant

pressure on both pre-deployment and post-deployment optimization processes. This is where service partitioning becomes a crucial strategy. By distributing service functions across domains while considering key constraints, such as limited visibility of the network state (due to privacy regulations or domain-specific data governance policies) and cost-driven overbooking, network operators can preserve performance and meet SLA commitments.

The 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) introduced End-to-End (E2E) logical network segmentation to enable per-service customization and management, powered by a range of technologies [1]. At the core, Software-Defined Networking (SDN) allows logically centralized, programmatic control of data flows. ETSI has been standardizing Network Functions Virtualization (NFV) that decouples Network Functions (NF) from dedicated hardware and enables scaling services as network demands evolve [2]. Service Function Chaining (SFC) adds another layer of dynamism, allowing for the dynamic linking of multiple NFs to create flexible, policy-driven services. Fig. 1 illustrates the process of SFC partitioning across multiple network domains.

Fig. 1: Illustration of SFC partitioning across multiple network domains. The left side presents a logical SFC composed of five interconnected VNFs. The right side shows the outcome of partitioning, where the VNFs are assigned to three separate domains: A, B, and C. Solid lines denote intra-domain connections, while dashed lines represent inter-domain links.

Finally, orchestration platforms integrate these technologies by automating network service lifecycle management, abstracting the complexities associated with creating, deploying, and reconfiguring network services and slices. This automation significantly reduces both Capital Expenditure (CAPEX) and Operational Expenditure (OPEX) by enabling efficient resource utilization, simplifying infrastructure management, and automating lifecycle operations, thereby lowering infrastructure investment and ongoing maintenance costs for telecommunication operators. However, the integration of heteroge-

neous domains, dynamic service requirements, and real-time decision-making introduces unprecedented orchestration complexity. Global service optimization algorithms have emerged to manage large-scale infrastructures involving multiple stakeholders and Infrastructure Service Providers (ISPs), raising privacy concerns among providers. Service partitioning alleviates these issues by logically dividing an SFC into segments, facilitating separation, scaling, and partial orchestration without requiring full visibility into each provider’s infrastructure.

Despite its advantages, Service Function Chain Partitioning (SFCP) poses a complex and challenging optimization problem. The difficulty lies in jointly determining the optimal partitioning strategy and the placement of each segment across multiple network domains with heterogeneous and dynamic characteristics, including variations in resource capacity, latency, mobility, and reliability. These domains—spanning terrestrial, aerial, satellite, and other network infrastructures—exhibit diverse behaviors that must be carefully considered to satisfy stringent QoS constraints. This involves balancing resource availability, QoS requirements, inter-domain routing overhead, and data locality considerations, often under incomplete or uncertain network state information. The combinatorial nature of possible partitioning and placement decisions, coupled with dynamic network conditions and policy constraints, makes SFCP a highly non-trivial problem, requiring scalable, intelligent, and privacy-preserving solutions.

In recent years, there has been a notable adoption rate of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) across a broad range of applications to optimize complex tasks. Studies have shown that these approaches can not only outperform humans, but also rival classical optimization techniques, all while reducing energy consumption, cost, and time [3], [4], [5]. Reinforcement learning (RL), in particular, has gained attention for its remarkable performance in decision-making and real-time control. Recently, the rise of Transformer-based architectures revolutionized the learning sector, offering unprecedented capabilities in processing and understanding language and large-scale datasets [6]. As these promising technologies continue to advance, they are increasingly being integrated into the networking domain, benefiting stakeholders across the spectrum, from end users to ISPs, particularly in the era beyond 5G, where efficiency and adaptability are critical.

To this end, we investigate the problem of efficient SFC partitioning and propose **Sequence-aware Differentiable Actor-Critic RL (SDAC)**, a novel method that integrates Transformer layers within a differentiable actor-critic RL framework. We evaluated the effectiveness of SDAC through an extensive and diverse simulation-based environment and compared it with multiple state-of-the-art methods to showcase its ability to maintain a higher long-term acceptance rate. The contribution of this work is threefold:

- We introduce a novel DRL framework, which leverages Transformer encoders within an actor-critic architecture to enable sequence-aware partitioning of SFCs. By leveraging the self-attention mechanism, our approach models inter-dependencies between VNFs, facilitating coordinated and parallel decision-making. Additionally, we introduce the ϵ -LoPe exploration strategy and Asymptotic

Return Normalization to enhance training stability and convergence. These innovations address the limitations of existing sequential and parallel VNF partitioning methods, significantly improving the efficiency and effectiveness of SFCP in multi-domain network orchestration.

- We introduce an innovative critic network, inspired by sentence encoders in Large Language Models (LLMs), that evaluates the entire sequence of VNF decisions holistically, providing a context-sensitive evaluation of the collective partitioning strategy. Alongside a relaxed representation for discrete actions, the policy can be updated in a fully differentiable manner, avoiding the stochastic sampling processes and credit assignment problem. Its adaptability to varying numbers of agents makes it a scalable solution for Multi-Agent Reinforcement Learning (MARL) problems, beyond the SFCP problem.
- We provide a comprehensive evaluation of SDAC through extensive simulations, demonstrating its superior performance compared to state-of-the-art methods, including DRL-based and (meta-)heuristic-based approaches. SDAC achieves higher long-term acceptance rates, improved resource utilization, and greater scalability while maintaining efficient inference times. These results validate the effectiveness of the proposed method in managing network resources under varying conditions.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II offers a discussion of related work. Section III gives a comprehensive introduction to the problem formulation and system model. Section IV details the proposed method. Section V describes the experimental setup. Section VI presents an extensive performance evaluation study. Finally, the conclusion and future directions are given in Section VII.

II. RELATED WORK

The transition of networking from hardware-oriented network architectures to flexible, software-driven ones has made service partitioning, along with related concepts such as SFC, Forwarding Graphs (FGs), and VNG-FG embedding, critical to system performance and reliability [2]. The increasing complexity of multi-domain networks [1], pushed recent literature efforts to integrate data-driven approaches into service partitioning strategies.

A. Optimization-based Approaches

Initially, researchers leaned on classical optimization-based algorithmic and heuristic approaches for SFC optimization, based on multiple criteria. Some notable examples related to our work include the following:

In [7], Quang et al., formulate the multi-domain VNF-FG embedding problem as an Integer Linear Programming (ILP) and utilize a heuristic algorithm for dynamic re-allocation. The authors in [8] study optimal network service decomposition and propose two algorithms, an ILP-based to minimize the cost of mapping, and a heuristic algorithm to solve the scalability issues of the ILP formulation, jointly studying the optimization of decomposition and embedding. The authors in [9] propose a Mixed Integer Programming (MIP) framework for optimal

virtual resource allocation in networked clouds, addressing the Virtual Network Embedding (VNE) problem with QoS constraints. Similarly, Dietrich et al. in [10] study the multi-provider Network Service Embedding (NSE), by decomposing the problem into SFC graph partitioning and mapping with ILP. The authors propose a centralized NSE orchestrator to address traffic scaling. Their evaluation emphasizes the optimization of the SFC graph partitioning and uncovers significant savings in service cost and resource consumption. The authors in [11] propose a hierarchical framework for virtual resource mapping in networked clouds, using Iterated Local Search (ILS) for cost-effective request partitioning among cloud providers and a Networked Cloud Mapping (NCM) approach for intra-domain resource embedding.

In [12], the authors propose a game theory-inspired graph partitioning framework, and prove mathematically that a Nash equilibrium exists for satisfying server affinity, collocation, and latency constraints of SFCs. The formulated partitioning game is based on the various components of an SFC that have to be split in a set of partitions and executed as VMs or containers in specific servers. Li et al. [13] address dynamic SFC mapping and scheduling for Internet of Vehicles (IoV) services, proposing two Tabu Search-based algorithms to solve a mixed-integer linear programming (MILP) problem. Their approach optimizes service provider profit by enabling VNF live migration, reinstantiation, and rescheduling, considering migration costs and delays across heterogeneous nodes.

Although most of these approaches guarantee convergence to a near-optimal solution, they suffer from scalability limitations due to the exponential growth of possible actions. Specifically, each SFC requires handling M^N potential actions, where M represents the number of available deployment targets and N denotes the number of VNFs within the SFC. This combinatorial explosion, coupled with the lack of adaptability and long convergence times, substantially limits the practicality in real-world scenarios.

B. Data-driven Approaches

To overcome the limitations of classical optimization-based methods and embrace scalability, researchers pivoted their focus on AI data-driven solutions due to their remarkable performance that challenged the *status quo* in networking.

The authors of [14] introduce an availability-aware SFC placement algorithm that leverages Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO). They evaluate the proposed algorithm by comparing it against two greedy algorithms in a variety of simulated scenarios using the Brazilian National Teaching and Research Network backbone topology.

In stark contrast to the *status quo*, newer solutions have emerged with multi-agent implementations. Specifically, in [15], Pentelas et al. argue that most SFCP works develop centralized implementation hinders scalability. They propose a cooperative multi-agent RL scheme for decentralized SFCP. Experimental results show that their scheme outperforms centralized Double Deep Q-Learning (DDQN) and further analyze the behavior and information exchange of the agents.

In a different note, Heo et al. in [16] propose a Graph Neural Network (GNN) based SFC model, which employs an

encoder-decoder architecture. The encoder extracts a representation of the network topology, while the decoder estimates the probabilities of neighboring nodes processing a VNF. To support their case, the authors argue that related works with high-level intelligent models such as Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) are not efficient in utilizing the topology information of networks and cannot be applied to dynamically changing topologies, as the models expect a fixed topology. Their solution outperforms the DNN-based baseline model in the conducted experiments.

Despite significant advancements, these works predominantly focus on either sequential or parallel VNF placement, each with inherent limitations. Sequential placement of VNFs, while offering strong coordination, is time consuming and constrained by the interdependence of prior decisions, which can impact overall efficiency [17], [18], [15]. Parallel VNF placement offers faster deployment, but suffers from weak coordination among VNFs, as individual placement decisions are made without full awareness of the broader context.

C. Transformers and their Applications

Recently Transformers have emerged as a groundbreaking architecture that disrupted Deep Learning (DL) research by demonstrating outstanding results. The use of attention mechanisms enables the effective modeling of complex, long-range dependencies within data sequences. The authors in [6] propose the groundbreaking DNN architecture of Transformers and demonstrate the remarkable results in natural language translation. Based on that, several studies [19], [20], [21] have showcased the successes of the architecture in various fields such as computer vision, natural language processing, audio processing and robotics.

In the field of next-generation communication networks, authors in [22] discuss how the strong representation capabilities of Transformers can be used in wireless network design. Particularly, they explore various solutions for massive Multiple-Input Multiple-Output (MIMO) beamforming and semantic communication problems. A recent work applies Transformers to automatic modulation classification [23], showing improved accuracy at low Signal-to-Noise Ratios (SNRs) and fewer model parameters compared to existing methods. A temporal Transformer was proposed for real-time QoS prediction in heterogeneous Internet of Things (IoT) applications [24], leveraging attention mechanisms for both short- and long-term sequence dependencies. Evaluated on diverse IoT traffic datasets, the model demonstrated robust and accurate QoS metric predictions. The authors in [25] propose a beamforming approach for 6G mmWave networks, combining a lightweight Transformer-CNN hybrid with multimodal data to ensure consistent QoS in dynamic environments. The method outperformed state-of-the-art baselines in beam prediction accuracy, received power, and efficiency across diverse scenarios.

While researchers are actively investigating the use of Transformers in beyond 5G and 6G networking scenarios, substantial gaps remain in this area, particularly regarding their effective integration into practical, real-time network optimization and orchestration tasks.

In summary, although data-driven methods improve scalability and long-term performance over optimization-based ones, parallel decision-making often overlooks inter-VNF dependencies, while sequential decision-making captures them at the cost of computational efficiency. To address these gaps, we propose a Transformer-based actor-critic framework that models SFCs as token sequences, enabling parallel, context-aware, and scalable decision-making for efficient SFC partitioning.

III. PROBLEM FORMULATION

To effectively address the SFCP problem, we begin with a high-level overview, followed by a comprehensive description of the system model. This model serves as the foundation for capturing the interplay between the substrate network, SFC requests, and the constraints governing resource allocation. By formalizing these elements, we enable the optimization of long-term system performance while adhering to resource capacity and latency constraints.

A. Problem Description

An SFC is defined as an ordered sequence of VNFs that enforces a flow processing policy on network traffic. For example, a typical SFC might consist of VNFs such as *VPN Gateway* \rightarrow *Firewall* \rightarrow *Encryption/Decryption* \rightarrow *Packet Inspection*, ensuring secure and efficient flow management for network applications. Each VNF in the SFC requires specific computing resources (e.g., CPU) to process the network traffic, while the connections between consecutive VNFs, referred to as virtual links (vLinks), consume network bandwidth for traffic forwarding. These VNFs and vLinks are hosted on a multi-datacenter system, where Data Centers (DCs) offer computing resources via their servers, and the physical links within and between DCs provide the necessary bandwidth.

In network orchestration, SFC partitioning can occur in single-domain or multi-domain settings. In single-domain settings, a centralized controller manages the entire substrate network and makes decisions based on fine-grain information from all Point of Presences (PoPs) or DCs. In contrast, multi-domain settings often involve decentralized control, where different domains (e.g., geographically distributed networks) operate independently, and only limited information can be shared between domains. In this work, we focus on the multi-domain setting, where the centralized Network Functions Virtualization Orchestrator (NFVO) has access only to *aggregated resource statistics* (e.g., total available CPU and bandwidth) of each PoP. However, the limited granularity of information exchanged between the PoPs and the NFVO introduces significant uncertainty, as the NFVO cannot observe the exact state of the resource distribution within each PoP [15].

In the context of SFC management, *partitioning* typically refers to the process of logically dividing an SFC into smaller sub-chains or groups of VNFs without immediate consideration of the substrate network, whereas *embedding* refers to the subsequent mapping of VNFs or sub-chains onto physical resources. However, in the literature, the term *partitioning* is sometimes used broadly to describe both the *partitioning* and *embedding* phases together, particularly when the focus is on

mapping VNFs across different domains or infrastructures. In this work, for clarity, we refer to *partitioning* as the mapping of VNFs at the inter-DC level, while *embedding* refers to the fine-grained mapping of VNFs within a single DC (intra-DC). Specifically, VNFs are mapped to PoPs, such as DCs, while vLinks are mapped to physical paths consisting of multiple physical links that connect the assigned PoPs.

The SFCP problem becomes challenging due to the following factors:

- **Resource Constraints.** Each PoP and physical link has limited CPU and bandwidth resources. Mapping VNFs and vLinks must respect these capacity limits.
- **Latency Constraints.** An SFC must meet its *E2E latency* requirement, ensuring that network flows traverse the chain of VNFs within a specified *SLA*.
- **Limited Visibility.** The system considers the settings where PoPs provide only *aggregated descriptive statistics* (e.g., total available CPU and bandwidth). This limitation imposes uncertainty when making decisions at the NFVO.
- **Resource Fragmentation.** Even if aggregated resource capacity at a DC is sufficient to host a VNF, the VNF may still fail to be accommodated due to fragmented resources across the servers within the DC.
- **Long-Term Acceptance Rate.** A mapping strategy that focuses excessively on optimizing on the current request may lead to inefficient resource allocation and fragmentation, making it difficult to accommodate subsequent requests. For example, aggressively placing VNFs on low-latency data centers without considering future resource availability might leave scattered, unusable resources in data centers. Over time, this short-sighted strategy could reduce the overall acceptance rate.

To summarize, the objective of SFCP is to find a strategy that places the VNFs and their corresponding vLinks onto the substrate network such that (i) The resource constraints are satisfied; (ii) The E2E latency requirement is met; and (iii) The long-term *acceptance rate* is maximized.

Fig. 2: Architecture and flow of the NFVO with the proposed decision-making module (SDAC) for SFC partitioning.

In this work, we consider a scenario where the embedding of partial SFCs within each DC is handled locally by its corresponding Virtual Infrastructure Manager (VIM). The focus of this work lies solely on the partitioning of SFCs at the

NFVO level. The integration of the proposed decision-making component (introduced in Section IV-B) within the NFVO for SFC partitioning is illustrated in Fig. 2. The process involves the interaction among the SFC requests, the NFVO, and the VIMs. The steps of this process are detailed as follows:

Step 0: Reception of the SFC Request. The process starts with the NFVO receiving an SFC request through the Northbound Interface (NBI). The SFC request typically comprises a sequence of VNFs, denoted as $VNF_0, VNF_1, \dots, VNF_n$, which must be deployed between a source (src) and a destination (dst) target DC. Upon receipt, the NFVO processes the request and extracts corresponding features, which may encompass the resource demands of each VNF, latency constraints, bandwidth requirements, and other QoS parameters.

Step 1: Retrieval of the State of NFVIs. In the following, the NFVO retrieves the current state of the Network Function Virtualization Infrastructures (NFVIs) through the Southbound Interface (SBI). The SBI enables communication between the NFVO and the underlying VIMs, denoted as $VIM_0, VIM_1, \dots, VIM_m$, each of which manages a corresponding DC (DC_0, DC_1, \dots, DC_m). The NFVO gathers monitoring data regarding the available resources across these VIMs, including computational capacity and networking resources of the DCs.

Step 2: Decision Making using the Joint State. The NFVO consolidates the processed SFC request (from Step 0) with the current state of the underlying infrastructure (from Step 1) and forwards this joint information to the decision-making module (introduced in Section IV-B).

Step 3: Delivery of Results for Deployment. Upon receiving the assignments from the decision-making module, the NFVO distributes these results to the respective VIMs through the SBI. The results specify the allocation of VNFs within the SFC across the DCs. For instance, VNF_0 might be assigned to DC_1 , while VNF_1 and VNF_2 could be co-located to DC_3 , depending on resource availability and objectives. Each VIM subsequently embeds the assigned VNFs within its corresponding DC, ensuring that the SFC is instantiated and operational in accordance with the partition assignments.

B. System Model

Substrate Network. The substrate network, denoted as $G_s = (V_s, E_s)$, is modeled as a graph where V_s is the set of Data Centers (DCs), each $u \in V_s$ with a CPU capacity of C_u (in units of available CPU resources) and E_s is the set of physical links between data centers, each $l \in E_s$ with a bandwidth capacity of B_l and latency L_l . The *inter-DC latency* is modeled as the sum of latencies along the shortest path between two DCs, computed using *Dijkstra's algorithm*. We consider intra-DC latency as negligible, thus only inter-DC latency contributes to the overall E2E latency.

SFC Requests. SFC requests are received sequentially over time, with one request arriving during each time slot t . For simplicity, the notation t is omitted in this section, as we focus on the context within a single time slot. Each request is modeled as a 6-tuple $(G_v, t_{arr}, t_{\Delta}, L_{SLA}, src, dst)$. $G_v = (V_v, E_v)$ represents the SFC as a directed graph, with

TABLE I: Notation Table

Notation	Description
G_s	Substrate network graph with DCs as nodes and inter-DC links as edges.
V_s	Set of data centers.
E_s	Set of physical links between data centers.
B_l	Bandwidth capacity of the physical link $l \in E_s$.
L_l	Latency of the physical link $l \in E_s$.
\tilde{C}_u	Aggregated remaining CPU capacity of DC $u \in V_s$.
\tilde{B}_u	Aggregated remaining bandwidth capacity of DC $u \in V_s$.
G_v	SFC request graph with VNFs as nodes and virtual links as edges.
V_v	Set of VNFs in the SFC.
E_v	Set of virtual links between VNFs in the SFC.
D_v	CPU demand of VNF $v \in V_v$.
D_e	Bandwidth demand of the virtual link $e \in E_v$.
L_{SLA}	End-to-end latency SLA for an SFC request.
$x_{v,u}$	Binary variable: 1 if VNF v is assigned to DC u , 0 otherwise.
$y_{e,l}$	Binary variable: 1 if the virtual link e is mapped to the physical link l , 0 otherwise.
δ	Binary variable: 1 if the request is successfully admitted, 0 otherwise.

V_v the set of VNFs, each $v \in V_v$ with a CPU demand of D_v and E_v the set of virtual links between VNFs, each $e \in E_v$ with a bandwidth demand of D_e . T_{arr} is the arrival time, t_{Δ} is the service lifetime and L_{SLA} is the E2E latency constraint for the request. The *src* and *dst* are two auxiliary VNFs with zero resource requirements ($D_{src} = D_{dst} = 0$) that represent the endpoints of the SFC. Accordingly, two additional edges are introduced to the service graph: (i) the edge from *src* to the first VNF $v_1 \in V_v$ and (ii) the edge from the last VNF $v_{|V_v|} \in V_v$ to *dst*.

The objective is to assign each $v \in V_v$ to a DC $u \in V_s$, ensuring that the SFC's E2E latency satisfies L_{SLA} , while respecting the resource limitations of the substrate network.

Partitioning Decision. The *partitioning decision* is made at the NFVO level, which assigns each VNF $v \in V_v$ to a specific DC $u \in V_s$:

$$x_{v,u} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if VNF } v \text{ is assigned to DC } u, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

At the time of making this decision, the NFVO only has *aggregated information* of the available resources in each DC:

- \tilde{C}_u : the sum of remaining CPUs in DC u .
- \tilde{B}_u : the sum of available bandwidth for links associated with DC u .

The actual embedding of VNFs inside each DC (e.g., mapping VNFs to individual computing nodes within the DC) is handled by the corresponding VIM of each DC. In contrast, the NFVO is responsible for inter-DC partitioning decisions, determining how VNFs are distributed across different DCs, rather than handling placements within a single DC. Additionally, the *mapping of virtual links* in E_v is decided implicitly at the same time when the VNF-to-DC mapping is determined. The shortest paths between assigned DCs are computed using *Dijkstra's algorithm*, and virtual links are mapped to the corresponding substrate links in E_s , without the need to explicitly decide on link mappings.

Resource Constraints. The following defines the key constraints on CPU and bandwidth capacities, alongside the issue of resource fragmentation.

- **CPU Capacity.** The CPU demand of VNFs assigned to a DC must not exceed its aggregated capacity:

$$\sum_{v \in V_v} D_v \cdot x_{v,u} \leq \bar{C}_u, \quad \forall u \in V_s. \quad (2)$$

- **Bandwidth Capacity.** There are two types of bandwidth constraints to consider:

- **Intra-DC Bandwidth Capacity Constraint.** The bandwidth demand for virtual links mapped within a DC must not exceed the aggregated bandwidth capacity of that DC:

$$\sum_{e \in E_v} D_e \cdot x_{v_1,u} \cdot x_{v_2,u} \leq \bar{B}_u, \quad \forall u \in V_s, \quad (3)$$

where \bar{B}_u is the aggregated bandwidth capacity available within DC u , and $x_{v_1,u}$ and $x_{v_2,u}$ indicate whether two consecutive VNFs (v_1, v_2) associated with the virtual link e are assigned to DC u .

- **Inter-DC Bandwidth Capacity Constraint.** The bandwidth demand for virtual links mapped between DCs must not exceed the remaining bandwidth capacity of the physical links between them:

$$\sum_{e \in E_v} D_e \cdot y_{e,l} \leq B_l, \quad \forall l \in E_s, \quad (4)$$

where $y_{e,l}$ indicates whether the virtual link e is mapped to the physical link l .

- **Resource Fragmentation.** Despite the aggregated resource demands described in formula (2) and (3) are satisfied for a given request, the request could still be rejected due to *resource fragmentation*, where:

- Available resources are scattered across multiple computing nodes within a DC, making it impossible to allocate sufficient contiguous resources to meet the request's demands.
- Similarly, bandwidth fragmentation on physical links within a DC can hinder the successful mapping of virtual links even if the total available bandwidth is sufficient.

Thus, meeting the aggregated resource demands is a *necessary but not sufficient condition* for accepting an SFC request.

E2E Latency Constraint. The E2E latency L_{e2e} is computed by traversing the VNFs v_1, v_2, \dots, v_k in the SFC sequentially and summing the inter-DC latencies between the DCs they are mapped to:

$$L_{e2e} = \sum_{e \in E_v} L_l \cdot y_{e,l}, \quad \forall l \in E_s, \quad (5)$$

where $y_{e,l} = 1$ if the virtual link e is mapped to the substrate link l . The E2E latency must satisfy the SLA:

$$L_{e2e} \leq L_{SLA}. \quad (6)$$

Objective. The goal is to maximize the *long-term acceptance rate* of SFC requests, where acceptance occurs only if all resource and latency requirements are satisfied. This can be formulated as:

$$\max_{\{\mathbf{x}(t)\}_{t=1}^T} \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \delta_t(\mathbf{x}(t)),$$

$$\text{where } \delta_t(\mathbf{x}(t)) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if the request at time } t \text{ is accepted,} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

Here, $\mathbf{x}(t)$ denotes the assignment of decision variables at time t defined in (1). The overall constraints below are the *necessary conditions* for achieving $\delta_t(\mathbf{x}(t)) = 1$:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{u \in V_s} x_{v,u}(t) &= 1, \quad \forall v \in V_v(t), \\ \sum_{v \in V_v(t)} D_v(t) \cdot x_{v,u}(t) &\leq \bar{C}_u(t), \quad \forall u \in V_s, \\ \sum_{e \in E_v(t)} D_e(t) \cdot x_{v_1,u}(t) \cdot x_{v_2,u}(t) &\leq \bar{B}_u(t), \quad \forall u \in V_s, \\ \sum_{e \in E_v(t)} D_e(t) \cdot y_{e,l}(t) &\leq B_l(t), \quad \forall l \in E_s, \\ \sum_{e \in E_v(t)} L_l \cdot y_{e,l}(t) &\leq L_{SLA}(t). \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

IV. PROPOSED METHOD

Building on the problem formulation, we now present our proposed approach to address the SFCP problem. Given the NP-hard nature of SFCP [26], we reformulate the problem as a Markov Decision Process (MDP), enabling us to leverage RL techniques for a scalable and efficient solution. This section is organized into two parts: (i) the MDP formulation, where we define the states, actions, transitions, and rewards for the problem, and (ii) the proposed DRL solution, where we detail our DRL approach.

A. MDP Formulation

To solve the SFCP problem using reinforcement learning, we first model it as an MDP. An MDP is defined as a 4-tuple $(\mathcal{S}, \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{T}, \mathcal{R})$, consisting of:

States (\mathcal{S}). The state captures the characteristics of an *individual VNF* within an SFC request and the *substrate network state*, represented as a vector:

$$s = [s_{req}, s_{sub}], \quad (9)$$

where:

- $s_{req} = [D_v, D_e, T_{arr}, t_{\Delta}, T_{SLA}, src, dst]$ represents the **request state**, with the individual elements defined in Section III-B.
- $s_{sub} = [\bar{C}, \bar{B}]$ represents the **substrate state**, where:
 - $\bar{C}_i \in [\bar{C}_1, \bar{C}_2, \dots, \bar{C}_m]$ is the aggregated remaining CPU resources at data center i .
 - $\bar{B}_i \in [\bar{B}_1, \bar{B}_2, \dots, \bar{B}_m]$ is the aggregated remaining bandwidth at data center i .

- m is the total number of data centers.

It is important to note that while the state s for each VNF within the same SFC shares the same s_{sub} , the s_{req} component will differ based on the resource requirements of the VNF.

Actions (A). The action specifies the target DC for mapping each VNF in the SFC request. Formally, let $V_v = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\}$ denote the set of VNFs in the SFC request, and $V_s = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_m\}$ represent the set of available DCs in the substrate network. An action $a_i \in \mathcal{A}$ for VNF $v_i \in V_v$ is represented as a one-hot vector of size m , where:

$$a_i = [a_i^1, a_i^2, \dots, a_i^m] \in \{0, 1\}^m, \quad \sum_{j=1}^m a_i^j = 1. \quad (10)$$

Here, $\arg \max(a_i) = j$ explicitly identifies the index j of the DC u_j to which the VNF v_i is assigned.

Transitions (T). The transitions describe how the state evolves as a result of an action. After taking an action a in state s :

- The **substrate state** s_{sub} is updated to reflect the resources consumed by the embedded VNFs and their virtual links. If the embedding fails, the substrate state remains unchanged. Additionally, resources consumed by *expired services* are released back into the substrate.
- The **request state** s_{req} transitions to the next incoming SFC request, with its resource demands, arrival time, service lifetime, and SLA.

The transition function $\mathcal{T}(s, a)$ ensures that the new state s' reflects both the updated substrate state and the attributes of the next SFC request. The detailed steps of this process are provided in Section V-A.

Rewards (R). The reward evaluates the outcome of the partitioning decision:

$$r(s, a) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if the request is accepted,} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

A reward of 1 is assigned if the SFC request is accepted, meaning all VNFs are successfully embedded, and the E2E latency satisfies the SLA. A reward of 0 is assigned if the request is rejected, either due to a failure in embedding any VNF or a violation of the SLA. Note that this immediate reward reflects the acceptance indicator δ in (7).

Objective. The goal is to maximize the expected cumulative discounted reward over time, which is formulated based on the standard RL framework. Formally, let $r(s_t, a_t)$ denote the reward received at time step t , and $\gamma \in [0, 1]$ be the discount factor, the objective is to learn a policy π that maximizes the expected cumulative discounted reward:

$$\mathbb{E}_{\tau \sim \pi} \left[\sum_{t=0}^T \gamma^t r(s_t, a_t) \right], \quad (12)$$

where T is the time horizon, and the expectation is taken over the trajectories τ induced by the policy π . This formulation reformulates the problem in III-B as an MDP, enabling its solution via DRL algorithms.

B. The Proposed Framework: SDAC

We propose a DRL framework, named **Sequence-aware Differentiable Actor-Critic RL**, for efficient SFC partitioning. Our approach incorporates Transformer encoders in both the actor and critic networks, leveraging their ability to model inter-dependencies among VNFs and make informed, coordinated decisions, as shown in Fig. 3. Below, we detail the components of the framework.

Algorithm 1: Learning Framework of SDAC

```

Initialize actor network  $\pi_\theta$  and critic network  $Q_\phi$ 
Initialize target networks  $\pi_{\theta'} \leftarrow \pi_\theta$  and  $Q_{\phi'} \leftarrow Q_\phi$ 
Initialize replay buffer  $\mathcal{D}$ 
Initialize perturbation factor  $\epsilon$ 
for  $episode = 1$  to  $N$  do
  Reset environment and observe the initial state  $s_0$ 
  for  $t = 1$  to  $total\ number\ of\ SFC\ requests$  do
    // Parallel Action Selection
     $a_t \leftarrow \epsilon\text{-LoPe}(s_t, \pi_\theta, \epsilon)$ 

    // Environment Interaction
    Run action  $a_t$ , get reward  $r_t$  and next state  $s_{t+1}$ 
    // Transition Storing
    Store transition  $(s_t, a_t, r_t, s_{t+1})$  in  $\mathcal{D}$ 
    // Critic Update
    Sample  $M$  mini-batch transitions  $(s, a, r, s')$ 
    from  $\mathcal{D}$  and compute target Q-values:
     $y \leftarrow r + \gamma Q_{\phi'}(s', \pi_{\theta'}(s'))$ 
    Update critic by minimizing the loss:
     $\mathcal{L}_{critic} = \frac{1}{M} \sum (Q_\phi(s, a) - y)^2$ 

    // Actor Update
    Update actor by minimizing the loss:
     $\mathcal{L}_{actor} = -\frac{1}{M} \sum Q_\phi(s, \pi_\theta(s))$ 

    // Target Network Update
    Update target networks:
     $\phi' \leftarrow \tau\phi + (1 - \tau)\phi'$ 
     $\theta' \leftarrow \tau\theta + (1 - \tau)\theta'$ 
  end
end
return  $\pi_\theta$ 

```

Actor-Critic Framework. The actor-critic architecture is a widely used framework in DRL that involves:

- **Actor Network.** The actor generates the actions (partitioning decisions for VNFs) based on the current state of the system. It learns a policy $\pi_\theta(s)$ that maps states s to actions a .
- **Critic Network.** The critic evaluates the quality of the actions proposed by the actor by estimating the Q-value, $Q_\phi(s, a)$, which represents the expected cumulative reward for taking action a in state s .

Fig. 3: Overview of the SDAC framework with Transformer-based architecture for sequence-aware SFC partitioning.

During training, the actor and critic are updated iteratively, with the critic providing feedback to guide the actor toward optimal policies. This architecture enables stable and efficient learning, as the critic guides the actor’s updates while the actor improves the policy.

Transformer Layers. The Transformer architecture [6], originally proposed for NLP tasks, is known for its ability to model relationships between input tokens using self-attention. A Transformer encoder layer comprises two main components: a multi-head self-attention mechanism and a Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP). Furthermore, there are two common Transformer encoder variants: Post-Norm, where layer normalization follows the residual blocks, and Pre-Norm, where Layer Normalization precedes the residual blocks. Post-Norm can result in unstable training due to the compounded effects of residual connections and Layer Normalization placement, whereas Pre-Norm provides more stable weight updates [27].

In the SFCP problem, the VNFs within an SFC are highly inter-dependent because the partitioning decision for one VNF can significantly influence the feasibility and performance of partitioning for other VNFs. By interpreting each VNF as a “token” and the entire SFC as a sequence, the Transformer-based actor and critic can effectively account for these inter-dependencies. Concretely, the prediction process resembles a sequence-to-sequence translation, where the VNF sequence is “translated” into a corresponding sequence of target DC indices. This formulation allows the model to efficiently map VNFs to their target DCs while exploiting the contextual relationships within the SFC.

- **Self-Attention for Inter-Dependency Modeling.** The self-attention mechanism, a core component of Transformers, allows the model to capture inter-dependencies between input elements by dynamically computing attention weights. For a sequence of n VNF tokens denoted as:

$$S = \{s_1, s_2, \dots, s_n\} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times d}, \quad (13)$$

where s is defined in (9) and d is its dimension. Self-attention computes a weighted combination of all tokens for each token in the sequence, resulting in S' . Specifically, self-attention involves three key steps:

Projection of Input. Project the input embeddings into query Q , key K , and value V matrices:

$$Q = S \cdot W_Q, \quad K = S \cdot W_K, \quad V = S \cdot W_V, \quad (14)$$

where $W_Q, W_K, W_V \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d_k}$ are learned projection matrices, and d_k is the dimension of the query vector Q and key vector K . It is a hyperparameter of the Transformer model, typically smaller than the input dimension d .

Computation of Attention Scores. Compute attention scores E using the dot product of queries and keys, scaled by the dimension d_k :

$$E = \text{softmax} \left(\frac{QK^\top}{\sqrt{d_k}} \right), \quad (15)$$

where $E \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ contains attention weights, representing the importance of each token with respect to others.

Weighted Sum of Values. Compute the output as a weighted sum of values:

$$S' = E \cdot V. \quad (16)$$

This mechanism allows each VNF token to attend to all other tokens, capturing their inter-dependencies. This means that the partitioning decision for one VNF incorporates information on the resource demands and constraints of other VNFs, enabling coordinated decisions.

- **Actor Network with Transformers.** The actor uses Transformer encoder layers to process the sequence of VNFs in the SFC. The input to the actor is the set of tokens of the entire SFC S , as defined in (13). This matrix is passed through the Transformer encoder layers. The actor outputs a probability distribution over the target DCs for each VNF, representing the policy $\pi_\theta(s)$. Specifically, the policy can be expressed as:

$$\pi_\theta(S) = [\pi_\theta(s_1), \pi_\theta(s_2), \dots, \pi_\theta(s_n)], \quad (17)$$

where $\pi_\theta(s_i) = a_i$ is a one-hot vector that encodes the selected action over the available DCs for the i -th VNF.

- **Critic Network with Transformers.** The critic $Q_\phi(s, a)$ also adopts Transformer encoder layers to process the sequence of VNFs and their corresponding partitioning

decisions. Instead of evaluating each decision individually, the critic evaluates the entire sequence of state-actions for the SFC as a whole. In particular, the input to the critic encodes the entire SFC, represented by the state matrix S defined in (13), concatenated with the partitioning decisions A , where $A = [a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n]$ represents the assignment of each VNF to a specific DC. Formally, the input to the critic is defined as:

$$H = [h_1, h_2, \dots, h_n], \quad (18)$$

where $h_i = [s_i; a_i]$, s_i is the feature of the i -th VNF, a_i is the one-hot representation of the partitioning decision for i -th VNF, and $[\cdot; \cdot]$ denotes concatenation. The output of the Transformer is then pooled into a single fixed-length vector using element-wise mean pooling. This approach borrows the idea from Universal Sentence Encoder (USE) architecture [28] commonly used in NLP tasks, where variable-length sequences are mapped into fixed-length representations. The pooled representation is then passed through a linear layer to compute the Q-value, providing a holistic evaluation of the decisions for the entire SFC.

- **Target Networks** To stabilize training, two target networks are employed for both the actor $\pi_{\theta'}(s)$ and critic $Q_{\phi'}(s, a)$. A target network is a separate network used to compute the target values for updates to the main network. This separation prevents the network from chasing its own moving predictions, which can lead to instability or divergence in training. The target network’s parameters are updated less frequently or with a smoothing mechanism (e.g., Polyak averaging) to improve convergence:

$$\phi' \leftarrow \tau\phi + (1 - \tau)\phi', \quad \theta' \leftarrow \tau\theta + (1 - \tau)\theta', \quad (19)$$

where $0 < \tau \ll 1$ is the target update rate.

While several studies have proposed sophisticated inter-decision communication mechanisms to improve the coherence of VNF placements, these approaches often introduce significant complexity, complicating both optimization and implementation. In contrast, the use of Transformers offers an elegant and well-validated solution for achieving coordination without unnecessary complexity.

Training Process and Objectives. The training process adopts the standard actor-critic framework, which uses separate loss functions for the actor and critic networks. The complete training steps are given in Alg. 1 and 2.

- **Critic Loss.** The critic is trained to minimize the Mean Squared Error (MSE) between the predicted Q-value $Q_{\phi}(s, a)$ and the target Q-value y . The target Q-value is computed using the Bellman equation:

$$y = r + \gamma Q_{\phi'}(s', \pi_{\theta'}(s')), \quad (20)$$

where r is the immediate reward, γ is the discount factor, and $Q_{\phi'}$ and $\pi_{\theta'}$ are the target critic and actor networks, respectively. The critic loss is defined as:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{critic}} = \mathbb{E} \left[(Q_{\phi}(s, a) - y)^2 \right]. \quad (21)$$

- **Actor Loss.** The actor is trained to maximize the Q-value of the actions it generates, as evaluated by the critic.

This is equivalent to minimizing the negative expected Q-value:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{actor}} = -\mathbb{E} [Q_{\phi}(s, \pi_{\theta}(s))]. \quad (22)$$

By leveraging the critic’s evaluation, the loss function guides the actor to update its policy in the direction that increases the Q-value, ultimately improving decision-making performance.

Continuous Action Representation. In the proposed framework, the decision to assign each VNF to a specific target DC is inherently a discrete action, which typically requires stochastic sampling, which is non-differentiable. To enable E2E training using gradient-based optimization, we employ a softmax layer on the actor’s output to represent actions. The softmax function serves as a smooth and differentiable approximation of the argmax operation [29], generating a relaxed one-hot vector that encodes the selected action.

This approach effectively transforms the discrete decision-making problem into a continuous one, avoiding the need for stochastic sampling processes typically required for discrete action spaces in DRL, allowing gradients to propagate directly through the softmax layer during backpropagation. This continuous approximation bridges the gap between continuous and discrete actions, enabling fully differentiable hybrid policy optimization. Particularly, in formula (18), the input H to the critic, formed by a concatenation of continuous states and relaxed discrete actions, enables seamless gradient flow through both the actor and critic networks. In addition, because the joint action vector is optimized in a single differentiable step, it inherently avoids the credit assignment problem that commonly arises in MARL settings. In general, this technique not only simplifies the training process, but also potentially accelerates convergence by enabling *E2E differentiability* through continuous representations of discrete actions.

Epsilon-Logit Perturbation (ϵ -LoPe). Since discrete actions are encoded as continuous representations, the traditional ϵ -greedy exploration strategy becomes inapplicable. To this end, we introduce ϵ -LoPe, a noise injection strategy that facilitates exploration. Instead of selecting a random action with probability ϵ , ϵ -LoPe perturbs the logits before applying softmax, imposing the exploration at the representation level rather than in the final actions. Specifically, at each decision step, a Gaussian noise $\eta \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$ is scaled by the decaying perturbation factor $\epsilon \in [0, 1]$ and added to the logits z_t :

$$\tilde{z}_t = z_t + \epsilon \cdot \eta, \quad (23)$$

where z_t represents the pre-softmax logits generated by the actor network. The perturbed logits \tilde{z}_t are then passed through a softmax function to produce the final action:

$$a_t = \text{softmax}(\tilde{z}_t). \quad (24)$$

The perturbation factor ϵ decreases over episodes, encouraging high exploration in early training while gradually moving toward deterministic policy as training progresses. To regulate the impact of noise injection, we apply z-score normalization to the logits z_t across features for each sample before adding the noise. This normalization ensures that the scale of logits

remains comparable to the noise η sampled from the standard normal distribution. In addition, the noise is scaled by a constant c , which serves as a hyperparameter to control the magnitude of the noise. The step in (23) is thus updated to:

$$\tilde{z}_t = \frac{z_t - \mu(z_t)}{\sigma(z_t)} + \epsilon \cdot c \cdot \eta, \quad (25)$$

where $\mu(z_t)$ and $\sigma(z_t)$ are the mean and standard deviation calculated across the elements of the logit vector z_t . This normalization ensures the effectiveness of the noise, preventing it from being either overly dominant or insignificant. The complete process is given in Alg. 2. By introducing perturbation at the logit level rather than overriding the final action, ϵ -LoPe enables natural action exploration, making it a robust exploration strategy for relaxed discrete action spaces.

Algorithm 2: ϵ -LoPe

Input: state s_t , actor π_θ , perturbation factor ϵ

// Compute Pre-Softmax Logits

Obtain raw logits from π_θ before applying softmax:

$$z_t \leftarrow \pi_\theta^{\text{logit}}(s_t)$$

// Generate Exploration Noise

Sample noise from a standard normal distribution:

$$\eta \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$$

// Perturb Logits with Noise

Add noise to normalized logits:

$$\tilde{z}_t \leftarrow \frac{z_t - \mu(z_t)}{\sigma(z_t)} + \epsilon \cdot c \cdot \eta$$

// Compute the Final Action

Apply softmax to obtain the final action:

$$a_t \leftarrow \text{softmax}(\tilde{z}_t)$$

return a_t

Asymptotic Return Normalization. In DRL, reward normalization is a widely used technique to improve training stability and convergence. Since raw rewards can have varying magnitudes across different tasks and environments, normalizing them helps prevent issues like vanishing or exploding gradients. Common approaches include reward clipping [30], standardization (z-score normalization), and scaling by an empirical or adaptive factor. These techniques ensure that updates remain within a stable range for efficient learning.

When training Transformer-based models in large-scale networks, hacky techniques such as model pretraining, learning rate warm-up and gradient normalization are commonly used to stabilize training [31], [32]. Although our experiments are conducted on a relatively smaller scale, we also observed training instabilities when these techniques were not applied.

To address this issue without introducing additional complexity, we propose Asymptotic Return Normalization (ARN), a simple yet effective normalization technique. Instead of applying patchwork stabilization methods, ARN normalizes

the immediate reward such that the expected cumulative discounted reward (i.e., the return) is scaled to the interval $[0, 1]$. This normalization prevents gradient explosion caused by occasional extreme return values, ensuring smoother training dynamics and improved convergence stability.

We derive the normalization factor as follows: Given an immediate reward $r_t \in [0, 1]$, the expected cumulative discounted reward G_t over N steps with discount factor γ is defined as:

$$G_t = r_t + \gamma r_{t+1} + \gamma^2 r_{t+2} + \dots + \gamma^{N-1} r_{t+N-1}. \quad (26)$$

This forms a finite geometric series with a common ratio of γ , where $0 < \gamma < 1$. The sum of this series is given by:

$$G_t = \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \gamma^k r_{t+k}. \quad (27)$$

Since the rewards are bounded as $0 \leq r_t \leq 1$, the maximum possible value of G_t occurs when all rewards take their upper bound (i.e., $r_t = 1$ for all steps):

$$G_{\max} = \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \gamma^k, \quad (28)$$

and using the formula for the sum of a finite geometric series:

$$G_{\max} = \frac{1 - \gamma^N}{1 - \gamma}. \quad (29)$$

To determine the normalization factor, we calculate the theoretical maximum possible return as $N \rightarrow \infty$. Since $0 < \gamma < 1$, the term γ^N approaches 0 as $N \rightarrow \infty$, giving us the infinite sum:

$$G_{\max} = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \gamma^k = \frac{1}{1 - \gamma}. \quad (30)$$

Thus, the return should ideally be normalized as:

$$G'_t = \frac{G_t}{G_{\max}} = (1 - \gamma)G_t = (1 - \gamma) \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \gamma^k r_{t+k}. \quad (31)$$

However, since we employ temporal difference learning approach, we do not explicitly compute the full return G_t at each step. Instead, we apply the normalization directly to the immediate reward to achieve the same effect. That is, we define the normalized reward as:

$$r'_t = (1 - \gamma)r_t. \quad (32)$$

This ensures that the return remains within $[0, 1]$, preventing the gradient explosion while preserving the structure of the reward signal, eliminating the need for ad-hoc techniques such as learning rate warm-up, model pretraining, and gradient normalization. Furthermore, the proposed ARN is task-agnostic, meaning it can be applied to any RL environment where the maximum return is known. By normalizing the reward signal based on this maximum return, the method ensures compatibility across diverse tasks without requiring task-specific adjustments, making it highly versatile and broadly applicable.

The experiment comparing ARN against various normalizing techniques is presented in Section VI-E.

V. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

To evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed framework, we conduct a comprehensive performance assessment. This section is structured into three parts: (i) the evaluation scenario, which provides details about the simulation environment; (ii) the comparison algorithms, including state-of-the-art (meta-)heuristic and DRL-based approaches; (iii) the configurations of hyper-parameters for the algorithms.

A. Evaluation Scenario

To capture the inherent heterogeneity and variability of multi-domain mobile network environments, we adopt a generalized simulation approach rather than modeling a specific deployment scenario. Domain characteristics such as resource capacities and service lifetimes varied over a wide range of values. Multiple independent simulation runs are conducted to ensure that the diversity and dynamics of domain conditions are sufficiently reflected. The simulation environment consists of a total of 10,000 linear SFC requests, each comprising 2 to 10 VNFs, uniformly distributed [11]. Each VNF requires between 5% and 20% of the CPU resources, also uniformly distributed [15]. The arrival of SFC requests follows a Poisson process, with an average rate of $\lambda = 0.05$ requests per time unit. To model evolving traffic intensity over time, the average rate λ is modulated by a sinusoidal function given as:

$$\lambda' = \lambda * 0.5 \cdot \left(\sin\left(\frac{i \cdot 2\pi}{N}\right) + 1 \right) \cdot 0.9 + 0.1, \quad (33)$$

where N is the total number of steps and i is the current step [33]. The service lifetime for each request is sampled from an exponential distribution with a mean of 1,000 time units [11]. The SLA for each request, expressed in terms of E2E latency requirements, is sampled uniformly from the range [2, 4] time unit. The auxiliary VNFs, src and dst , which represent the endpoints of the SFC, are independently assigned to randomly selected DCs. The substrate network comprises 5 data centers, modeled as a random graph initialized using the *Erdős-Rényi model*, where each possible edge occurs with a probability of 0.5. Each DC contains a number of computing nodes sampled uniformly from the set {32, 64, 128, 256}. The initial load on these computing nodes varies between 70% and 100%, also sampled uniformly. The bandwidth capacity of all links is assumed to be sufficient at all times [15]. For determining the E2E latency of a service request, *Dijkstra's algorithm* is applied to compute the shortest path between the DCs hosting consecutive VNFs once all VNFs in an SFC are assigned. Each inter-DC link is assigned a latency of 1 time unit, i.e., $L_l = 1$ in formula (5), while the latency for intra-DC links is assumed to be negligible. The complete simulation operates as follows:

- 1) **Process Incoming Request.** The system receives the next SFC request along with its partitioning assignment, as predicted by the algorithm. This assignment specifies the target DCs for embedding the VNFs within the SFC.

- 2) **Handle Expired Services.** The system checks for any expired services, releases their allocated resources, and updates the substrate network state to reflect the latest available resources.
- 3) **Estimate Resource Feasibility.** The system evaluates whether the resources required by the SFC, based on the assignment from Step 1 and the formulas in Section III-B, are available in the target DCs. If the resource requirements cannot be met, the request is rejected, and the system proceeds to Step 1 to handle the next request.
- 4) **Check SLA Compliance.** If the resource requirements are satisfied in Step 3, the system verifies whether the E2E latency of the SFC meets the specified SLA using formulas in Section III-B. If the latency requirement is fulfilled, the request is accepted, and the target DCs proceed with embedding the corresponding VNFs. Otherwise, the request is rejected, and the system moves to Step 1 for the next request.

This flow ensures that each incoming request is processed in a structured manner, accounting for resource availability and SLA compliance, while dynamically managing the system's state to handle evolving service demands.

B. Comparison Solutions

To evaluate the effectiveness of our proposed solution, we compare it with five representative algorithms, including both heuristic and state-of-the-art methods. These algorithms are described as follows:

- **Greedy Policy (GP).** In this greedy heuristic-based approach, used as a baseline for comparison, the SFC is not partitioned. Instead, the entire SFC is assigned to a single DC that has the maximum remaining resource capacity at the time of decision-making. While this method reduces the complexity of partitioning, it may lead to inefficient utilization of resources, particularly for longer SFCs, and can result in higher rejection rates due to capacity constraints. This approach serves as a baseline for evaluating more advanced partitioning methods.
- **Iterated Local Search (ILS).** ILS is a meta-heuristic optimization method that iteratively refines solutions by applying local search techniques with perturbation to escape local optima [34]. This state-of-the-art solution is well-suited for partitioning and embedding problems, as demonstrated in prior research [11]. The original ILS algorithm, however, considers only resource constraints in the optimization process, without accounting for latency-related metrics. To address this limitation, we modify the algorithm to prioritize minimizing E2E latency for the current SFC request while adhering to resource constraints. The modified ILS framework operates as follows:
 - 1) **Initial Assignment.** Generate an initial assignment for the SFC by randomly mapping each VNF to an available DC.
 - 2) **Perturbation.** With a given probability, each VNF's assigned DC is altered to a randomly selected DC.
 - 3) **Local Search.** Perform local search by selecting a random VNF from the SFC and iterating over all

available DCs. The VNF is temporarily reassigned to each DC, and the DC that yields the minimum latency while satisfying resource constraints in (2) is chosen for reassignment.

- 4) **Acceptance Criterion.** Accept the newly obtained assignment if it achieves a lower E2E latency compared to the current best assignment. Otherwise, retain the existing best assignment.
- 5) **Iterative Refinement.** Repeat steps 2–4 until the E2E latency constraint is met, or the predefined maximum number of iterations is reached.

Despite its strengths, the nature of ILS does not account for long-term performance, which may lead to over-provisioning of resources for the individual request. This can result in future requests being rejected due to insufficient resources, thereby impacting the overall system efficiency over time. It serves as a strong optimization-based benchmark for comparison.

- **Risk-Aware Iterated Local Search (RAILS).** RAILS extends the standard ILS by incorporating online risk models to predict the acceptance probability of assignments for each domain [33]. Unlike ILS, which evaluates resource feasibility based on aggregated available resources, RAILS maintains a DC-specific risk model that dynamically estimates the likelihood of acceptance given (i) the aggregated available resources, (ii) total resource demands, and (iii) the total number of VNFs to be placed there. Specifically, for DC d , let P denote the probability of acceptance for assigning a set of VNFs, given the input features \mathbf{x} (the DC subscript d is omitted as we here focus on a single DC). The risk model can be expressed as:

$$P(\mathbf{x}) = f_{\theta}(R, D_{\text{total}}, N_{\text{total}}), \quad (34)$$

where the feature vector $\mathbf{x} = (R, D_{\text{total}}, N_{\text{total}})$ consists of the aggregated available resources at DC d , denoted as R ; the total resource demands of the VNFs to be placed at DC d , denoted as D_{total} ; and the total number of VNFs to be assigned to DC d , denoted as N_{total} . The function f_{θ} is a NN parameterized by θ . The risk model is built upon historical feedback, allowing the model to learn and adapt over time. While aggregated resource constraints must be met for a mapping to succeed, they alone do not guarantee acceptance. Risk models help capture these subtler admission control dynamics, which would otherwise be inaccurately estimated if relying solely on aggregate metrics. The workflow of RAILS closely resembles ILS, with the key difference being that feasibility evaluation is handled by risk models rather than directly assessing aggregated available resources as defined in (2). These risk models are updated periodically after a certain number of steps to reflect changing system conditions. The training of the risk model f_{θ} is performed by minimizing the cross-entropy loss, using historical feedback as labels. Formally, for a given DC d , let $y_i \in \{0, 1\}$ denote the binary feedback (1 for acceptance, 0 for rejection) for the sample i , and let $\hat{y}_i = f_{\theta}(\mathbf{x}_i) \in [0, 1]$ be the predicted probability given

feature vector \mathbf{x}_i . The loss function is defined as:

$$-\frac{1}{K} \sum_{i=1}^K [y_i \log(\hat{y}_i) + (1 - y_i) \log(1 - \hat{y}_i)], \quad (35)$$

where K is the number of feedback samples. The parameters θ are updated by minimizing this loss. The up-to-date risk models are then used to predict the acceptance probability of a request at a given DC. If the predicted probability \hat{y} exceeds a predefined threshold ρ_{risk} , the assignment is considered feasible. This approach bridges the gap between meta-heuristic-based optimization and data-driven decision-making, making it a more effective solution for SFC partitioning. Despite its advantages, RAILS, like ILS, does not explicitly optimize for long-term performance. While it enhances decision-making in the short term, it does not proactively manage resource availability across future requests.

- **Sequential DDQN (seqDDQN).** This state-of-the-art DRL-based solution employs Double Deep Q-Network (DDQN) to sequentially map VNFs one by one to target data centers. As one of the leading DRL methods for tackling the SFCP problem, seqDDQN inherently optimizes for long-term performance via Q-learning. The decision for each VNF is made with access to the action of the preceding VNF, allowing for a degree of coordination between assignments. In particular, the next state s' in the transition represents the entire SFC of the subsequent request. The Q-value of the next state-action is estimated by averaging the corresponding maximum Q-values across all VNFs in the next state. However, its sequential nature can result in longer decision-making times and may miss globally optimal solutions due to its stepwise approach. In this work, reward signals are shared between decisions within the same SFC. This method serves as a modern DRL-based benchmark for comparison.
- **Parallel DDQN (paraDDQN).** This approach also utilizes a DDQN-based policy as in seqDDQN, but maps all VNFs in parallel. By processing all VNFs simultaneously, paraDDQN achieves significant improvements in decision-making speed. However, the placements are determined independently, without explicit coordination among VNFs, which limits its ability to account for interdependencies effectively. To address this challenge, several studies have introduced sophisticated inter-decision communication mechanisms to enhance coordination among VNF assignments. Although these methods improve mapping coherence, they also add considerable complexity to the optimization process, increasing the difficulty of implementation and management. In this work, we adopt shared reward across agents, which enables agents to learn implicit coordination during training [35]. The key difference from seqDDQN is that predictions can be made in parallel, as the state of each VNF does not depend on the action of the preceding VNFs. This method achieves a balance between performance and computational efficiency, making it a robust modern DRL-based benchmark for comparison.

We compare our proposed method with the algorithms presented above, which include both (meta-)heuristic and DRL-based approaches. Each approach has unique strengths and design choices. Their key properties and distinguishing features are summarized in Table II.

C. Configurations

This subsection provides the configuration details of the methods used in this study. All experiments were performed on a server with an Intel Core i7-10700K CPU, 32 GB of RAM, and an NVIDIA RTX 2080 Super GPU. Python 3.11.9 and PyTorch 2.5.1 were used for the implementation.

- **ILS.** The maximum number of iterations for optimizing each SFC is set to $10 \times |\text{SFC}| \times |\text{DCs}|$, following the settings recommended by the authors in [11], ensuring sufficient exploration of the solution space per request.
- **RAILS.** The configuration follows that of ILS, with the addition of risk models. The risk model consists of a two-layer MLP with 32 neurons per layer, using the GELU activation function [36], Layer Normalization, and a residual connection. It maintains a memory size of 1000 and is updated every 100 steps using the AdamW optimizer with a learning rate of 0.01. The acceptance probability threshold ρ_{risk} is set to 0.5 by default.
- **paraDDQN and seqDDQN.** The Q-network constructed from two residual layers [37]. Each layer comprises two MLPs with a hidden dimension of 384, employing Layer Normalization and GELU activation. Sinusoidal positional encoding is utilized to encode positional information [6]. The ϵ -greedy strategy starts with $\epsilon = 1.0$ and decreases linearly by 0.1 each episode until it reaches 0.1. The replay buffer size is set to 10^6 . The discount factor γ is 0.99, and the learning rate is set to 10^{-4} . A batch size of 256 is used for training over 15 episodes. AdamW optimizer [38] is adopted for weight updates.
- **SDAC.** Both actor and critic networks consist of three Pre-Norm Transformer encoder layers. Each layer has a hidden dimension of 128, 8 attention heads, and an MLP dimension of 512. Sinusoidal positional encoding is employed to represent positional information. The learning rate for the critic is set to 10^{-4} , while the actor uses a lower learning rate of 10^{-5} . The soft update parameter τ for target networks is set to 10^{-3} . The ϵ -LoPe strategy starts with $\epsilon = 1.0$ and decreases linearly by 0.1 at the end of each episode until it reaches 0.1. The perturbation constant is empirically set to $c = 2$. Training is conducted with a batch size of 256 over 15 episodes using AdamW optimizer. Note that to ensure a fair comparison, the number of parameters in the actor of SDAC is matched to that of paraDDQN and seqDDQN.

To assess the performance of the algorithms, a comprehensive evaluation is conducted. A total of 10 substrate topologies are generated for the simulation environment using the *Erdős-Rényi model*, where each edge is included with a probability of 0.5. The proposed ARN (see Section IV-B) is applied to all DRL-based approaches. After training, the

topology that yields the median average reward for each algorithm is selected as the test instance, ensuring a representative evaluation. For each selected topology, 10 independent testing runs are performed using different random seeds to account for variability. The averages of the performance metrics obtained across these runs are reported in the subsequent section.

VI. EVALUATION METRICS AND RESULTS

This section presents an extensive performance evaluation of the proposed SDAC framework against state-of-the-art (meta-)heuristic and DRL-based methods for SFC problems. Through extensive simulations, we analyze key performance metrics, including long-term acceptance rates, scalability, causes of service request rejections, learning convergence, inference times, and resource utilization. Additionally, we compare the effectiveness of ARN against other normalization techniques in training stability and performance.

A. Acceptance Rate and Scalability

The long-term acceptance rate is a critical performance metric that measures the proportion of SFC requests successfully accepted over the entire evaluation period, as described in (7). It reflects the effectiveness of a partitioning algorithm in managing system resources and meeting SLA requirements.

Fig. 4: Acceptance and arrival rate over time.

Fig. 4 presents the acceptance rate of different algorithms over time (top) and the corresponding arrival rate of SFC requests (bottom). In the early phase of the simulation, the acceptance rate is relatively low for all algorithms due to high demands, as the arrival rate reaches its peak during this period. As the arrival rate gradually decreases, the system experiences reduced traffic intensity, leading to an improvement in acceptance rates. Among the algorithms, the proposed SDAC consistently outperforms the others throughout the simulation. In comparison, seqDDQN demonstrates competitive performance but lags behind SDAC, followed by paraDDQN. RAILS

TABLE II: Qualitative properties of the comparison algorithms.

Algorithm	Opt-based	ML-based	Long-term Performance	Parallel Decision	Sequence Aware	(Re-)Training Required	Risk Model
GP	✓			✓	✓		
ILS	✓			✓	✓		
RAILS	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓
seqDDQN		✓	✓		✓	✓	
paraDDQN		✓	✓	✓		✓	
SDAC		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	

Legend. Opt-based = classical optimization / (meta-)heuristic; ML-based = uses machine learning; Long-term Performance = explicit long-term reward optimization; Parallel Decision = decisions for all VNFs in one step; Sequence Aware = decision for one VNF explicitly accounts for others in the input sequence; (Re-)Training Required = requires online or offline (re-)training; Risk Model = maintains explicit admission-risk models.

performs poorly in the earlier steps due to the immaturity of its risk models, which require more time to converge. Despite this initial drawback, RAILS eventually achieves better performance than the ILS, though it remains inferior to DRL-based approaches. The GP shows the lowest acceptance rate, highlighting its inefficiency in managing resources in general. Overall, the results demonstrate that SDAC manages to sustain a higher acceptance rate even during high-traffic periods.

Fig. 5: Average acceptance rate.

Fig. 5 shows the average acceptance rate achieved by the different algorithms. SDAC exhibits the highest acceptance rate, while both seqDDQN and paraDDQN achieve competitive acceptance rates, although lower than SDAC. The stronger coordination of decisions in seqDDQN results in a performance advantage over paraDDQN. RAILS and ILS fall into the second tier, consistent with the results in Fig. 4. GP again obtains the lowest acceptance rate.

#VNFs	SDAC	seqDDQN	paraDDQN
2	0.999	0.999	0.997
4	0.984	0.983	0.975
6	0.917	0.903	0.884
8	0.822	0.810	0.774

TABLE III: Scalability comparison.

Table III shows the scalability of the three DRL-based algorithms in terms of acceptance rates as the number of VNFs increases. To evaluate scalability under controlled complexity, the trained models are tested on a modified request traffic set, where each service request contains exactly 2, 4, 6, or 8 VNFs, respectively. As the service complexity grows, all methods experience a gradual decrease in performance, which is expected due to the increased orchestration challenge. However, SDAC consistently maintains a higher acceptance rate

across all scales, highlighting its robustness and adaptability. seqDDQN also demonstrates strong scalability, outperforming paraDDQN. The performance gap increases as the number of VNFs increases, indicating the superior ability of SDAC to handle more complex requests.

B. Causes of Service Request Rejection

We analyze the causes of rejection for service requests during the partitioning process. Two primary factors contribute to the rejection:

- **Resource Capacity Violation.** The resource requirements of the SFC, when partitioned into groups, may exceed the available computational resources (e.g. CPU) in one or more target data centers. When this occurs, the SFC is rejected.
- **Latency SLA Violation.** If the resource capacity constraints are satisfied, the E2E latency is evaluated against the latency SLA. A service request is rejected if the latency exceeds the specified threshold, even if the resource capacity requirements are met.

Note that the evaluation of resource capacity feasibility takes precedence in the rejection process. If an SFC fails to meet the resource capacity requirements, the latency SLA is not evaluated, as the partition attempt is terminated at this stage.

Fig. 6 provides insights into the causes of service request rejections by distinguishing between resource capacity violations (CPU) and latency SLA violations. The figure highlights a clear trend in how different algorithms manage system constraints. Traditional heuristics such as GP and ILS show the highest overall violation ratios, with both CPU and SLA violations contributing significantly. In the case of GP, the majority

Fig. 6: Proportion of rejections caused by resource capacity violations vs. latency SLA violations.

of rejections stem from CPU constraints, indicating inefficient resource allocation strategies that lead to resource saturation. SLA violations also contribute a notable portion, suggesting poor latency-awareness. ILS shows a similar pattern, though with a lower total rejection rate, reflecting marginal improvements with latency-aware decision-making. RAILS, while showing better performance than GP and ILS, continues to exhibit a substantial rate of SLA violations. This suggests that although RAILS improves CPU allocation efficiency, it still struggles to meet strict latency requirements, potentially due to its limited consideration of long-term performance impacts during decision-making. In contrast, the DRL-based methods achieve significantly lower overall violation ratios compared to heuristic-based approaches. paraDDQN notably reduces CPU-related rejections, while maintaining a moderate level of SLA violations. seqDDQN further improves the overall rejection rate, but with a shift in the cause of violations, showing a slight increase in CPU-related violations while significantly reducing SLA violations. This suggests that seqDDQN places greater emphasis on meeting latency constraints, potentially at the expense of tighter resource allocation. SDAC outperforms all other approaches, exhibiting the lowest overall violation ratio. Similar to seqDDQN, SDAC shows a trade-off between CPU and SLA violations, incurring slightly more CPU-related rejections while achieving the lowest SLA violation rate among all methods. This indicates that SDAC prioritizes adherence to strict latency requirements, which is critical for service quality, even under resource constraints. The result highlights SDAC's effective coordination capabilities, allowing it to maintain high service acceptance with adequate management of key SLAs.

C. Learning Curves and Inference Time

We analyze the learning curves and inference time of the considered approaches. The learning curves depict the convergence behavior of the DRL-based models by showing the average testing rewards achieved over training episodes. Additionally, we evaluate the inference time per action, which measures the time taken by each method to make a single SFC partitioning decision during deployment.

Fig. 7: Average reward of DRL-based approaches over time.

Fig. 7 presents the learning curves of the three DRL-based approaches. These curves reflect how efficiently and

effectively each algorithm learns to optimize its policy over time. All three methods exhibit steady improvement, indicating successful learning and convergence. SDAC starts with a relatively high reward and demonstrates the most stable and consistent growth throughout the training process. It also converges faster than the other methods and reaches the highest average reward. seqDDQN also shows rapid learning, particularly after the initial episodes. Although it briefly dips in performance around episode 3, it quickly recovers and nearly matches SDAC by the end of training. paraDDQN, on the other hand, demonstrates slower and more gradual improvement. Its early-stage rewards lag behind the other two methods, and it converges to a slightly lower average reward. This suggests that while paraDDQN can learn effective policies, its parallel action structure may lead to less efficient coordination, resulting in comparatively slower convergence. Overall, the figure highlights the effective learning dynamics of SDAC, characterized by faster convergence, higher stability, and strong final performance.

Fig. 8: Inference time per request.

Fig. 8 presents the inference time per request on a logarithmic scale, highlighting significant differences in computational efficiency. GP is the fastest, with an inference time of 0.004 ms, reflecting its simplicity. ILS and RAILS exhibit the highest inference times, at 5.931 ms and 58.21 ms, respectively, due to their iterative optimization processes, with RAILS incurring additional overhead from handling risk models. Among DRL-based methods, paraDDQN achieves the lowest inference time of 0.480 ms, benefiting from parallel processing, while seqDDQN and SDAC are slightly slower but remain within a reasonable range. Notably, when considered alongside the acceptance rates shown earlier in Fig. 5, SDAC achieves a strong balance between performance and efficiency. It maintains the highest acceptance rate while keeping inference time low.

D. Resource Utilization

To evaluate the effectiveness of partitioning strategies, it is essential to analyze how computational resources are utilized across different DCs. Proper resource utilization not only ensures efficient operations but also reduces the likelihood of resource fragmentation, which can impact the acceptance rate of future SFC requests. This analysis considers two key metrics during peak hours, defined as the time periods with the highest demand for resources:

- **Average Resource Utilization.** The average resource utilization metric provides an overall measure of how effectively the computational resources across all DCs are used during peak hours. For a set of DCs V_S , the average resource utilization is defined as:

$$\frac{1}{|V_S|} \sum_{u \in V_S} \frac{\text{Resources Used at DC } u}{\text{Total Resources at DC } u}. \quad (36)$$

A higher value indicates better overall utilization of available resources, while a lower value suggests potential under-utilization.

- **Perplexity of Load Distribution.** The perplexity of resource utilization quantifies the distribution of resource usage across all DCs during peak hours. It reflects the degree of balance in resource allocation, where higher perplexity implies a more uniform distribution and lower perplexity indicates uneven utilization. For a set of DCs V_S , the perplexity is computed as:

$$\exp \left(- \sum_{u \in V_S} p_u \log(p_u) \right), \quad (37)$$

where p_u is the proportion of total utilized resources at DC u , given by:

$$p_u = \frac{\text{Resources Used at DC } u}{\sum_{v \in V_S} \text{Resources Used at DC } v}. \quad (38)$$

A higher perplexity value suggests that resource usage is evenly distributed across DCs, reducing the risk of overloading specific DCs, while a lower value indicates concentration of resource usage in a few DCs.

Fig. 9: Average CPU utilization over peak hours.

Fig. 9 shows the average resource utilization over time, which highlights the superior acceptance rate achieved by SDAC, with seqDDQN and paraDDQN following closely behind. This trend is consistent with the behavior observed in Fig. 5. As shown in the figure, SDAC consistently achieves the highest CPU utilization, peaking above 0.91. This indicates that SDAC makes the most effective use of available computational resources, which contributes directly to its high acceptance rates. Its ability to efficiently pack services onto infrastructure under heavy load reflects strong decision-making and orchestration capabilities. seqDDQN and paraDDQN also exhibit high CPU utilization, though slightly lower than SDAC. seqDDQN maintains a slight advantage over

paraDDQN across the time steps, consistent with its more coordinated decision-making framework. RAILS shows moderate utilization, gradually improving toward the end of the interval, but still trailing behind the DRL-based approaches.

On the other end of the spectrum, ILS and GP demonstrate the lowest CPU utilization. GP, in particular, maintains a consistently conservative resource usage pattern, suggesting a more cautious allocation strategy. While this may help avoid overloading the system, it results in significant underutilization of available resources and ultimately limits acceptance performance. Overall, the CPU utilization trends during peak hours strongly correlate with the algorithms' effectiveness, confirming SDAC's superior ability to adapt under pressure.

Fig. 10: Perplexity of load distribution over peak hours.

Fig. 10 illustrates the perplexity of load distribution over time, highlighting the balance of resource allocation across all DCs. The DRL-based methods maintain relatively high perplexity, indicating their ability to distribute resource usage evenly. In contrast, GP, ILS, and RAILS exhibit consistently lower perplexity, suggesting a more conservative approach that concentrates resource usage in fewer DCs. In particular, SDAC sustains high perplexity throughout the timeline and remains unaffected by noticeable drops, demonstrating its robustness in optimizing resource allocation over time.

E. Asymptotic Return Normalization

To assess the impact of different normalization techniques on training stability and performance, we evaluate SDAC under four strategies: the proposed ARN, without normalization (w/o Norm), gradient normalization (grad Norm), and z-score normalization (z-score Norm), respectively.

Fig. 11 demonstrates the impact of different return normalization strategies on SDAC's learning performance. The proposed ARN consistently leads to faster convergence and achieves the highest final rewards. While z-score normalization and training without normalization also reach competitive performance, their curves exhibit noticeable fluctuations even after convergence, indicating less stable policy updates. This instability is possibly due to *increasingly large Q-values as training progresses*, which can result in larger gradients and unstable updates. Gradient normalization performs less effectively overall, showing slower learning and lower final rewards. These results highlight the advantage of ARN in promoting both efficient learning and post-convergence stability.

Fig. 11: Effect of various normalization techniques on SDAC.

VII. CONCLUSION & FUTURE WORK

In this work, we proposed a novel Transformer-empowered Actor-Critic Reinforcement Learning framework for sequence-aware Service Function Chain (SFC) partitioning in multi-domain network orchestration. By integrating Transformer encoders within an Actor-Critic architecture, our method leverages the self-attention mechanism to model inter-dependencies among Virtual Network Functions (VNFs), enabling coordinated and parallel decision-making. The introduction of the ϵ -LoPe exploration strategy and Asymptotic Return Normalization (ARN) further enhances training stability and convergence, addressing the limitations of existing sequential and parallel VNF partitioning methods. Additionally, the innovative critic network, inspired by sentence encoders in Large Language Models (LLMs), enables holistic evaluation of VNF assignments, capturing contextual relationships within SFCs.

Comprehensive evaluations through extensive simulations demonstrate that our method outperforms state-of-the-art methods, including both Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL)-based and (meta-)heuristic-based approaches. The proposed method achieves higher long-term acceptance rates, improved resource utilization and scalability while maintaining efficient inference times. Furthermore, the proposed ARN technique ensures training stability, outperforming other normalization strategies in terms of convergence speed and final performance. These results validate the effectiveness of our method in optimizing SFC partitioning under the complexities of multi-domain networks, making it a robust solution for beyond 5G and 6G network environments.

The promising results of our method pave the way for several future research directions. First, validating and extending the proposed method using real-world network data is a critical step toward practical deployment. To address potential limitations in data availability, advanced generative AI techniques could be employed to synthesize realistic network traffic, thus enriching the training and evaluation process. Second, exploring the integration of our method with emerging technologies, such as digital twins or in-band telemetry, could enable more precise resource allocation and proactive network management by providing real-time insights into network states. Third, investigating a decentralized scheme for the proposed method to enhance scalability and robustness in

multi-domain settings. Specifically, designing a communication framework that allows limited information exchange tailored for attention mechanisms could facilitate distributed decision-making across multiple locations. This decentralized scheme is expected to reduce latency, enhance fault tolerance, and effectively handle imperfect information inherent in multi-domain network environments.

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